

EOSC Glossary

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EOSC Glossary Interest Group

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1 Introduction

The present document is intended as a basis for the terminological standardisation process within the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative, with the objective of facilitating and improving the actual communication between the different communities involved.

The realisation of the glossary follows a process of collection, harmonisation and validation of the definitions of the concepts, based on the analysis of the EOSC related documents and the review of the terminological collections, the standards and the specific literature connected to the concepts.

The collected definitions and formulations are analysed and compared in order to identify the characteristics that constitute a concept and, in particular, those that distinguish it from the others.

The set of characteristics that constitute a concept creates relationships with the ones of the other concepts. Those relationships are the basis for establishing a concept system, in which the position of a concept depends on its relationships with the others, thus creating a de facto hierarchy, which implies an inheritance system.

Each concept may be represented by one or more designations, which may be proper names (when a concept is correlated to a single object e.g. EOSC) or terms (when a concept is correlated to a class of objects e.g. infrastructure).

Since different concepts can be associated with the same term (homonymy) and different terms can be associated with the same concept (synonymy), especially if a glossary, such as the present one, spans multiple disciplines, overlappings are inevitable. In order to reduce ambiguity it is necessary for the communities involved to agree a common abstraction level in which monosemy can be achieved.

The coherence of the glossary is achieved through the concept system that, while improving the consistency of the glossary, imposes constraints on the definitions, heavily influencing the harmonisation process.

Already existing authoritative definitions are used when possible, even though it can be necessary to modify them during the harmonisation process (the modifications are indicated in the source section of the entry). While open access resources are preferred as a source, it has also been necessary to refer to closed ones.

The necessary new definitions are formulated reflecting the previously defined concept system with the intent to provide the means to avoid any confusion when referring to each different concept. They are as concise as possible, containing only those elements that are required to distinguish one concept from the others in the concept system, thus stating its superordinate concept and the necessary delimiting characteristics.

The terms are listed in alphabetical order. To facilitate usability references have also been made from the other preferred terms and from the admitted terms.

2 Entry structure

The entry structure is based on the standard ISO 10241-1:2011. Each term is preceded by an entry number. The preferred terms are written in bold and are followed by the admitted terms, if any. The definition may be preceded by a domain indication and can be followed by examples and notes to disambiguate, specify and clarify the context and the usage of the term.

If an entry is a quotation from another document, it is indicated at the end of it, accompanied by a modification statement, if that is the case. The source field is omitted if a definition has been created ad hoc or if it is the result of significant modifications.

entry number
preferred term
admitted term
<domain> definition

EXAMPLE

Note to entry:

[SOURCE:]

3 Terms and definitions

AAI

see [authentication and authorisation infrastructure](#).

AAI service

see [authentication and authorisation infrastructure service](#).

3.1

above the net service

above-the-net service

[added-value service](#) that enables [users](#) to communicate, interact and collaborate effectively in a heterogeneous and distributed federated environment.

[SOURCE: *Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 4. European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures)* (European Commission Decision C(2019)4575 of 2 July 2019). (2019).

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2018-2020/main/h2020-wp1820-infrastructures_en.pdf, modified – reference to services instead of applications and services.]

above-the-net service

see [above the net service](#).

3.2

access enabling service

[IT service](#) allowing [end-users](#) to easily exploit [EOSC resources](#) such as discovery, ordering and workflow enabling services.

EXAMPLE The [EOSC Portal](#).

[SOURCE: Donvito, G., Scardaci, D., Sanden, M. V. D., Nicotri, S., & Costantini, A. (2019).

D10.4 EOSC Hub Technical Architecture and standards roadmap v2.

<https://documents.egi.eu/public/RetrieveFile?docid=3495&filename=EOSC-hub%20D10.4%20v2%20Under%20EC%20review%20Public.pdf&version=4>, modified – reference to end-users instead of customers; reference to IT service.]

3.3

access policy

[policy](#) defining the obligations for authorizing access to a [resource](#).

[SOURCE: ISO 27789:2013, modified – reference to policy]

3.4

accounting

[process](#) of collecting resource usage measurements and apportioning charges for [services](#) provided by a [service provider](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC TR 26927:2011, modified – reference to service provider instead of network operator or service provider.]

3.5

accounting service

[IT service](#) that collects, stores, aggregates, and displays usage information of HTC compute, storage space, cloud VM and data set resources.

[SOURCE: Donvito, G., Scardaci, D., Sanden, M. V. D., Nicotri, S., & Costantini, A. (2019).

D10.4 EOSC Hub Technical Architecture and standards roadmap v2.

<https://documents.egi.eu/public/RetrieveFile?docid=3495&filename=EOSC-hub%20D10.4%20v2%20Under%20EC%20review%20Public.pdf&version=4>, modified – reference to IT service.]

3.6

activity

set of actions carried out within a [process](#).

[FITSM. (2016). *Part 0: Overview and vocabulary* (2.4). <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>.]

3.7

actor

individual or group that fulfils one or more roles in the [EOSC](#).

EXAMPLE A [research performing organisation](#) participating in the EOSC initiative as a [service provider](#) and as an [end-user](#).

added value service

see [added-value service](#).

3.8

added-value service

added value service

value-added service

value added service

VAS

[service](#) that is offered in addition to the core service in question thus creating additional [value](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 24760-1:2019]

3.9

administrative metadata

[metadata](#) necessary to allow the management of a [resource](#) in a [repository](#).

Note 1 to entry: Administrative metadata can be categorised as [provenance or context metadata](#), [technical](#), [rights](#) and [use metadata](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified – reference to metadata instead of information; reference to management instead of proper management; Note 1 to entry has been broken up into independent concepts; reference to use metadata; reference to resource instead of digital objects.]

3.10

aggregator

[IT service](#) that collects information about digital content from a variety of sources with the primary goal of increasing its discoverability, and possibly adding [value](#) to this information via processes like curation, abstraction, and classification, and linking.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Architecture Working Group, SIRS Task Force. (2020). *Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software*, modified – reference to IT service.]

API

see [application programming interface](#).

3.11

application programming interface

API

set of commands, functions and protocols that specify how software components should interact.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18598:2016]

3.12

architecture

<system> fundamental concepts or properties of a [system](#) in its environment embodied in its [components](#), relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011, modified – reference to components instead of elements.]

archive

see [repository](#).

3.13

authentication

[process](#) of verifying or disproving a claimed digital identity.

[SOURCE: e-Infrastructure Reflection Group. (2010). E-IRG “Blue Paper” 2010, modified – reference to digital instead of electronic.]

3.14

authentication and authorisation infrastructure

AAI

[ICT infrastructure](#) used to identify and authorise [users](#) of shared [resources](#).

Note 1 to entry: AAI includes [authentication and authorisation services](#), [components](#) for identity and privilege management, and the entities responsible for these [services](#).

[SOURCE: e-Infrastructure Reflection Group. (2010). E-IRG “Blue Paper” 2010, modified – reference to ICT infrastructure instead of systems.]

3.15

authentication and authorisation infrastructure service

AAI service

[IT service](#) that enables authenticated and authorised access to [resources](#).

[SOURCE: AARC Consortium Partners, ApplInt members, & Liampotis, N. (2019). Deliverable DJRA1.4: Evolution of the AARC Blueprint Architecture. https://aarc-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/AARC2-DJRA1.4_v2-FINAL.pdf, modified – reference to IT service.]

3.16 authorisation

[process](#) of deciding if a request to perform an action on a [resource](#) shall be granted or not.

[SOURCE: e-Infrastructure Reflection Group. (2010). E-IRG “Blue Paper” 2010.]

3.17 best practice

technique or methodology that, through experience and research, has proven to reliably lead to a desired result.

[SOURCE: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary. <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/>.]

3.18 big data

extensive [datasets](#) – primarily in the characteristics of volume, velocity, variety, and/or variability – that require a scalable [architecture](#) for efficient storage, manipulation, and analysis.

[SOURCE: NIST Big Data Public Working Group Definitions and Taxonomies Subgroup. (2015). NIST Big Data Interoperability Framework: Volume 1, Definitions (NIST SP 1500-1). National Institute of Standards and Technology. <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1500-1>.]

3.19 Board

body of the [governance structure](#) in charge of achieving the purpose and directing the activities by implementing the decisions, instructions and recommendations adopted by the [General Assembly](#).

Note 1 to entry: The Board is composed of a minimum of seven Directors, which are elected from the General Assembly amongst its Delegates, including the President, the Vice-President and the Treasurer. When there are fewer than seven [Members](#) the number of Directors is equal to the number of Members.

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL. https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf, modified – reference to body of the governance structure.]

3.20

catalogue and marketplace

end-user-facing EOSC Portal service enabling access, discovery, ordering and [composition](#) of the [resources](#).

3.21

certified repository

[repository](#) that has gone through and passed a certification process.

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia.
<https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>.]

3.22

citizen

citizen scientist

[user](#) who is an ordinary person having interest on one or several scientific disciplines (including, but not limited to, the open source community or commercial companies undertaking research). Citizens want to get information or contribute to a citizen science initiative or other initiatives of general public interest.

EXAMPLE Individuals to agree sharing anonymously their health conditions and track some lifestyle indicators such as sport activity receiving a feedback on their health status.

Note 1 to entry: EOSC Skills required: Light knowledge on the concept of [EOSC](#) (with special focus on privacy and legal boundaries); Basic ICT skills to use generic and specific applications and tools for citizen participation.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*.
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to end-user who is an ordinary person instead of Citizens targeted in EOSC are ordinary people.]

citizen scientist

see [citizen](#).

cloud based service

see [cloud-hosted service](#).

3.23

cloud computing

model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or [service provider](#) interaction.

Note 1 to entry: This cloud model is composed of five essential characteristics (On-demand self-service, Broad network access, Resource pooling, Rapid elasticity, Measured service), three service models (Software as a Service, Platform as a Service, Infrastructure as a Service), and four deployment models (Private cloud, Community cloud, Public cloud, Hybrid cloud).

[SOURCE: Mell, P., & Grance, T. (2011). *The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing. Recommendations of the National Institute of Standards and Technology* (Special Publication 800-145; Reports on Computer Systems Technology). National Institute of Standards and Technology, Information Technology Laboratory.
<https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/Legacy/SP/nistspecialpublication800-145.pdf>.]

3.24

cloud enhanced service

[IT service](#) provided by [users](#) of [cloud-hosted services](#).

[SOURCE: Botterman, M., & Cave, J. (2017). *The European Open Science Cloud Governance Model: Towards a new European decision making modelling to support Research and Innovation. Final Study Report*. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. <https://publications.europa.eu/s/mlip>, modified – reference to IT service.]

3.25

cloud infrastructure

[ICT infrastructure](#) that enables the five essential characteristics of [cloud computing](#).

[SOURCE: Mell, P., & Grance, T. (2011). *The NIST Definition of Cloud Computing. Recommendations of the National Institute of Standards and Technology* (Special Publication 800-145; Reports on Computer Systems Technology). National Institute of Standards and Technology, Information Technology Laboratory.
<https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/Legacy/SP/nistspecialpublication800-145.pdf>, modified – reference to ICT infrastructure instead of collection of hardware and software]

3.26

cloud service

[IT service](#) offered through [cloud computing](#) invoked using a defined interface.

Note 1 to entry: Such services may be at the Infrastructure-, Platform- or Software-as-a-Service levels.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 19944:2017, modified – reference to service instead of one or more capabilities; Note to entry: Lee, C. A., Bohn, R. B., & Michel, M. (2020). The NIST Cloud

Federation Reference Architecture (NIST SP 500-332). National Institute of Standards and Technology. <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-332>, modified – reference to IT service.]

cloud-based service

see [cloud-hosted service](#).

3.27

cloud-hosted service

cloud-based service

cloud based service

[IT service](#) made available to cloud service users.

Note 1 to entry: They overlap to a degree with [cloud services](#) – for example, data storage service provision can more closely resemble a hard drive or a database application.

Note 2 to entry: They are often provided by entities that contract with cloud platform providers to meet users' needs.

[SOURCE: Botterman, M., & Cave, J. (2017). *The European Open Science Cloud Governance Model: Towards a new European decision making modelling to support Research and Innovation. Final Study Report*. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. <https://publications.europa.eu/s/mlip>, modified – reference to IT service.]

coalition of doers

see [doers](#).

3.28

common service

generic service

[IT service](#) providing generic capabilities usable by any science discipline each supporting aspects of the [data lifecycle](#) from creation to [processing](#), [analysis](#), preservation, access and reuse.

EXAMPLE Examples of services belonging to this category are multi-disciplinary services for data discovery, processing, workflow management and orchestration, [data management](#), etc.

[SOURCE: Donvito, G., Scardaci, D., Sanden, M. V. D., Nicotri, S., & Costantini, A. (2019). *D10.4 EOSC Hub Technical Architecture and standards roadmap v2*. <https://documents.egi.eu/public/RetrieveFile?docid=3495&filename=EOSC-hub%20D10.4%20v2%20Under%20EC%20review%20Public.pdf&version=4>, modified – reference to IT service.]

3.29

competence

sum of [knowledge](#), skills and experience that an actor needs to effectively take on a specific role.

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). *Part 0: Overview and vocabulary* (2.4).

<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>, modified – reference to actor instead of individual or group.]

3.30**component**

<EOSC> discrete [actor](#), [service](#), [policy](#), [process](#), [data](#) or [infrastructure](#) that can be considered an asset or a part of the [EOSC](#)

3.31**component**

<system> discrete part of a [system](#)

3.32**composition**

result of assembling [resources](#) for a particular purpose.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to resources instead of collection of elements; Note 1 to entry has been removed.]

3.33**computing infrastructure**

[ICT infrastructure](#) enabling computational services.

consumer

see [end-user](#).

context metadata

see [provenance metadata](#).

CRIS

see [current research information system](#).

3.34**current research information system****CRIS**

research information management system

RIMS

database or other information system to store, manage and exchange contextual [metadata](#) for the research activity funded by a [research funder](#) or conducted at a [research-performing organisation](#) (or aggregation thereof).

Note 1 to entry: Within an [organisation](#) a CRIS can facilitate the cooperation between the researchers and the organisation management through the following roles: Research information for decision support; Metadata (index) to scholarly publications (white and grey) in a repository and to research datasets and software in a repository and as such the primary (registration) and leading metadata resource for institutional repositories; Access view to financial, human resource and project management information of an organisation (and to other relevant organisation systems); Provision of directory service information for authentication, authorisation, workflow and cooperative working; Generation of web pages presenting the organisation of intranet, DMZ and extranet, directly or from other organisational systems; Interoperation with other CERIF-CRIS (and their associated systems) to give a global view of research information; Being the local node and primary source of the institution's research information in national and international Research Information Infrastructures.

[SOURCE: Current research information system. (2020). In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Current_research_information_system; Note 1 to entry: euroCRIS. Why does one need a CRIS? <https://www.eurocris.org/why-does-one-need-cris>.]

3.35 data

reinterpretable digital representation of [information](#) in a formalized manner suitable for communication, interpretation, or [processing](#).

EXAMPLE Sequence of bits, code, measurements, recordings.

Note 1 to entry: Data in the [EOSC](#) are considered inherently digital.

[SOURCE: ISO 8000-2:2020, modified – added digital; EXAMPLE has been added; Note 1 to entry has been added.]

3.36 data analysis

[data life-cycle](#) stage that involves the techniques used to satisfy [analyst](#) goals of producing informative [knowledge](#) from organized [data](#).

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017.]

3.37 data analyst data scientist

[user](#) who is an expert on [data processing](#), not necessarily bounded to a specific discipline, capable of evaluating [data quality](#), extracting relevant [knowledge](#) from [data](#) or representing such knowledge.

EXAMPLE An expert who develops a general-purpose Machine Learning algorithm that could efficiently run in the [EOSC](#) federated RI.

Note 1 to entry: EOSC Skills required: Ability to use [EOSC-Core](#) and [EOSC-Exchange](#) services for data access and processing; Deep understanding of EOSC [FAIR data principles](#); Ability to design and develop new EOSC-exchange services related with [data analytics](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to user.]

data analytics

see [data processing](#).

3.38

data cleaning

data cleansing

data scrubbing

[process](#) used to improve [data quality](#) by detecting and correcting (or removing) defects and errors in [data](#).

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia. <https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>.]

data cleansing

see [data cleaning](#).

3.39

data curation

managed [process](#), throughout the [data life-cycle](#), by which [data](#) are [cleansed](#), documented, standardized, formatted and interrelated.

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017, modified – reference to data instead of data/data collections.]

3.40

data curator

[user](#) who is an expert on the [management](#) and oversight of an organization's entire [data](#) in compliance with policy and/or regulatory obligations for long-term preservation and to provide higher-level users with high quality data that is easily accessible in a consistent manner.

EXAMPLE An expert that collects and publishes a [dataset](#) of genomic samples related to the Flu with geographic annotation using domain-specific standard formats, ensuring the FAIRness of the data.

Note 1 to entry: [EOSC](#) Skills required: Deep understanding of [FAIR principles](#) and ability to use [EOSC-Core](#) and [EOSC-Exchange](#) services for data publication and preservation; Ability to validate the fulfilment of Open Science principles in EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange services related to data.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to user.]

3.41 data engineer

[user](#) operating at a low level close to the [data](#) who writes the code that handles data and moves it around.

[SOURCE: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Global Science Forum. (2020). *OECD GSF DRAFT Final Report: Building digital workforce capacity and skills for data-intensive science* (DSTI/STP/GSF(2020)6), modified – reference to user instead of people.]

3.42 data infrastructure

[ICT infrastructure](#) enabling the [data life-cycle](#).

3.43 data life-cycle

all stages in the existence of [data](#) from creation to destruction.

[SOURCE: RDA DFT IG. (2019). Term Definitions Version 4.0 "Philadelphia". <https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>, modified – reference to data instead of digital information.]

3.44 data management

[process](#) and associated activities of defining, creating, storing, maintaining and providing access to [data](#) in one or more information systems.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC TR 10032:2003, modified – reference to process instead of activities.]

3.45

data management plan

formal statement describing how [research data](#) will be managed and documented throughout a research project and the terms regarding the subsequent deposit of the [data](#) with a [data repository](#) for long-term [management](#) and preservation.

[SOURCE: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary. <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/>]

3.46

data manager

[user](#) responsible for the [management](#) of [data](#) and associated [metadata](#).

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). *DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia*. <https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>, modified – reference to user instead of person; reference to data instead of data elements/digital object content.]

data on-boarding

see [data onboarding](#).

3.47

data onboarding

data on-boarding

[resource onboarding](#) where inputs characterise [data](#) stored in an already onboarded [repository](#) and the intended result is the inclusion of those data into the [EOSC](#).

3.48

data processing

data analytics

[process](#) that performs a series of actions on [dataset\(s\)](#) to distil [information](#).

Note 1 to entry: It may be applicable at any stage in the [data lifecycle](#) from quality assurance and event recognition close to data acquisition to transformations and visualisations to suit decision makers as results are presented.

Note 2 to entry: Data analytics methods draw on multiple disciplines, including statistics, quantitative analysis, data mining, and machine learning. Very often these methods require compute-intensive infrastructures to produce their results in a suitable time, because of the data to be processed (e.g. huge in volume or heterogeneity) and/or because of the complexity of the algorithm/model to be elaborated/projected.

[SOURCE: Zhao, Z., & Hellström, M. (Eds.). (2020). *Towards Interoperable Research Infrastructures for Environmental and Earth Sciences: A Reference Model Guided Approach for*

Common Challenges (Vol. 12003). Springer International Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52829-4>.]

3.49

data quality

multi-dimensional construct perception and/or a judgment of [data](#)'s fitness or trustworthiness to serve intended research uses in a given context.

Note 1 to entry: Data quality is often expressed along a continuum from low to high based on a number of perceived attributes of data. This includes: Relevance to research issues and timeliness, Accuracy (the degree of congruity between data object and real world phenomena), Precision/accuracy (limit of all practical analytic and rational interpretations of a data object), Completeness (no gaps in coverage), Consistency(internal and external), and understandability (informativeness including via associated documentation and capturing provenance of changes).

Note 2 to entry: Data quality is improved via [data cleaning](#).

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia.
<https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>]

data repository

see [repository](#).

3.50

data research infrastructure support professional

[user](#) who is an ICT expert who manages and operates [research infrastructures](#) and the necessary [services](#) for its use on the processing of [research data](#).

EXAMPLE The administrator of a cloud or storage infrastructure that exposes access to the [resources](#) as [EOSC services](#).

Note 1 to entry: EOSC Skills required: Knowledge on the EOSC principles; ability to deploy and maintain [EOSC-Core](#) and [EOSC-Exchange](#) services related to processing and storage, or to data resources such as repositories and databases.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*.
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbc1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to user.]

data scientist

see [data analyst](#).

data scrubbing

see [data cleaning](#).

data set

see [dataset](#).

3.51

data steward

[data manager](#) delegated the responsibility for [managing](#) a specific set of data resources who is an expert on the preparation and treatment of [data](#) including data selection, storage, preservation, annotation provenance and other [metadata](#) maintenance, and dissemination.

EXAMPLE An expert that validates, recodes, trims or any other action on each source Dataset of genomic samples related to the Flu to guarantee that they can be properly used and integrated according to domain-specific standard formats.

Note 1 to entry: [EOSC](#) Skills required: Deep understanding of [FAIR principles](#) and ability to use [EOSC-Core](#) and [EOSC-Exchange services](#) for data publication and preservation; Ability to validate the fulfilment of Open Science principles in EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange services related to data.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to data manager; reference to delegated the responsibility for managing a specific set of data resources from ISO 8000-2:2020.]

3.52

data stewardship

formalized [data management](#) and oversight of an [organization's data](#) to help provide [end-users](#) with high-quality data that is easily accessible in a consistent manner.

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia.

<https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>, modified – reference to data management instead of management; reference to data instead of data assets/resources; reference to end-users instead of business users.]

3.53

data wrangler

[user](#) converting [data](#) into a usable form so that they can be easily used with automated or semi-automated tools.

[SOURCE: *Open Data Handbook Glossary*. <http://opendatahandbook.org/glossary/en/>, modified – reference to user instead of person.]

3.54

data wrangling

[process](#) of manually or semi-automatically converting or mapping [data](#) from one form into another format that allows for [data processing](#) with the help of semi-automated tools.

[SOURCE: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary. <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/>, modified – reference to data processing instead of data consumption.]

3.55

dataset

data set

logically meaningful group of [data](#).

3.56

descriptive metadata

[metadata](#) about the content and identifying characteristics of a [resource](#) that aids in finding or understanding it.

[SOURCE: Riley, J., & National Information Standards Organization (U.S.). (2017).

Understanding metadata: What is metadata, and what is it for?

<http://www.niso.org/publications/understanding-metadata-riley>, modified – reference to resource.]

digital ecosystem

see [ecosystem](#).

3.57

digital infrastructure

[infrastructure](#) constituted by a physical layer (hardware) and an abstraction layer (software) that is based on the physical one.

Note 1 to entry: Digital infrastructures, unlike physical ones, are generative: they can be used recursively to create new digital infrastructures.

3.58

digital object

DO

any set of [data](#) and an associated unique identifier.

Note 1 to entry: A digital object allows to bind all critical information about any entity together, including [research data](#), software, scientific workflows, hardware designs, protocols, provenance logs, publications, presentations, etc., as well as all their [metadata](#) (for the complete object and for its constituents).

[SOURCE: Kahn, R. E., & Ely, D. K. (2000). *United States Patent: 6135646 - System for uniquely and persistently identifying, managing, and tracking digital objects* (Patent No. 6135646).

<http://patft.uspto.gov/netacgi/nph-Parser?Sect1=PTO1&Sect2=HITOFF&d=PALL&p=1&u=%2Fnexthtml%2FPTO%2Fsrchnum.htm&r=1&f=G&l=50&s1=6,135,646.PN.&OS=PN/6,135,646&RS=PN/6,135,646>, modified – reference to data instead of sequences of bits or digits; Note 1 to entry: Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M., Choirat, C., Sanden, M. van de, & Coppens, F. (2020). *EOSC Interoperability Framework* (Draft for Community Consultation v1.0). EOSC Executive Board, FAIR Working Group and Architecture Working Group.]

3.59

digital platform

software-based [external platform](#).

Note 1 to entry: A software-based external platform consists of the extensible codebase of a software-based system that provides core functionality shared by the modules that interoperate with it and the interfaces through which they interoperate.

[SOURCE: Ghazawneh, A., & Henfridsson, O. (2015). *A paradigmatic analysis of digital application marketplaces*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jit.2015.16>.]

digital repository

see [repository](#).

3.60

disciplinary repository

[domain repository](#) aimed at a specific discipline.

DO

see [digital object](#).

3.61

doers

coalition of doers

[organisations](#) that attended the EOSC Summit in June 2017 and signed the EOSC Declaration which committed to implement the vision of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) while open to new entrants willing to participate in the effort.

[SOURCE: Council of the European Union. (2018). COUNCIL CONCLUSIONS on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (9291/18 RECH 224 TELECOM 150 IND 142 MI 392 COMPET 364 DATAPROTECT 102 ECOFIN 484 CYBER 113).

https://www.consilium.europa.eu/register/en/content/out/?&typ=ENTRY&i=ADV&DOC_ID=ST-9291-2018-INIT.]

3.62

domain repository

[research data repository](#) aimed at a specific domain.

3.63

dynamic data

[data](#) subject to frequent or real-time updates, in particular because of their volatility or rapid obsolescence.

EXAMPLE: Data generated by sensors are typically considered to be dynamic data.

[SOURCE: DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), modified – reference to data instead of documents in a digital form.]

3.64

e-infrastructure

[ICT infrastructure](#) enabling digital [services](#) for data- and computing-intensive research in virtual and collaborative environments.

[SOURCE: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/e-infrastructures>, modified – reference to ICT infrastructure.]

3.65

ecosystem

<actor> set of [actors](#) with varying degrees of multi-lateral, non-generic complementarities that are not fully hierarchically controlled

[SOURCE: Jacobides, M. G., Cennamo, C., & Gawer, A. (2018). Towards a theory of ecosystems. *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(8), 2255–2276. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2904>.]

3.66

ecosystem

digital ecosystem

<system> distributed, adaptive, open socio-technical [system](#) with properties of self-organisation, scalability and sustainability inspired from natural ecosystems.

[SOURCE: Briscoe, G., & De Wilde, P. (2009). *Computing of Applied Digital Ecosystems*. 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1643823.1643830>]

3.67

emergent behaviour

functions and purposes performed and carried out by a [system](#) that do not reside in any of its

[components](#).

[SOURCE: Maier, M. W. (1996) *Architecting Principles for Systems-of-Systems* INCOSE International Symposium, Vol. 6, Issue 1, doi: [10.1002/j.2334-5837.1996.tb02054.x](https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.1996.tb02054.x).]

3.68

end-user

consumer

[user](#) who will ultimately be exploiting a [resource](#) or resources in accordance with the [policies](#) governing their use.

EOSC

see [European Open Science Cloud](#).

EOSC Association

see [European Open Science Cloud Association](#).

3.69

EOSC enabler

[researcher](#) of the discipline with technical and open science skills that can design and partially implement discipline-specific applications using [EOSC services](#) and [data](#), who will act as a bridge between the scientific community and the technical services.

EXAMPLE A researcher with technical skills who integrates a common Genomic data processing suite so it runs on EOSC Federated Research Infrastructure (RI) consuming Data which is discoverable and is properly formatted, accessible and reusable.

Note 1 to entry: EOSC Skills required: Ability to use [EOSC-Core](#) and EOSC exchange services; Deep understanding of EOSC FAIR data principles; Ability to design and coordinate the development of new High-level EOSC discipline-specific services.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>.]

EOSC interoperability framework

see [interoperability framework](#).

3.70

EOSC Partnership

co-programmed European Partnership between the [EOSC Association](#) and the European Commission that will consolidate the outputs of EOSC projects from Horizon 2020 and further develop [EOSC](#) through structured funding in Horizon Europe and in-kind contributions from the member countries and [stakeholders](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board. (2020). Draft proposal for a European Partnership under Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership. https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he-partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf.]

3.71

EOSC Portal

[IT service](#) enabling [resource onboarding](#) and providing online access to and use of the [resources](#).

[SOURCE: Glossary—EOSC hub—EGI Confluence.

<https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/Glossary#Glossary-EOSCPortal>, modified – reference to IT service; reference to resource onboarding; reference to enabling instead of providing.]

EOSC resource

see [resource](#).

3.72

EOSC-Core

federating core

[digital platform](#) providing the functionality that is required to enable open science practices to occur across domains and countries according to the [EOSC interoperability framework](#).

Note 1 to entry: The EOSC-Core consists of the minimum set of [components](#) necessary to provide the means to discover, share, access and re-use [resources](#).

Note 2 to entry: It includes the [federating services](#).

Note 3 to entry: It provides a standard mechanism for naming and locating [data](#) and [services](#), a mechanism for discovery of and access to [resources](#) across the [ecosystem](#) and a common framework for managing user identity and access.

Note 4 to entry: The EOSC-Core does not, itself, provide the means to transfer, store, process or preserve [research data](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Sustainability Working Group. (2020). *Solutions for a sustainable EOSC: A FAIR Lady (olim Iron Lady) report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/870770>.]

3.73

EOSC-Exchange

set of [common](#) and [thematic services](#) complementing the [EOSC-Core](#) that stores and exploits [FAIR data](#) encouraging its reuse.

EXAMPLE Examples of services included in the EOSC-Exchange are those that store, preserve or transport research data as well as those that compute against it.

Note 1 to entry: EOSC-Exchange is accessible through the [catalogue and marketplace](#).

3.74

European Open Science Cloud

EOSC

the [federation of systems](#), regulated by the [Rules of Participation](#), resulting from the activities and initiatives promoted by the European Commission to support its [policies](#) on [open science](#) and [open innovation 2.0](#).

Note 1 to entry: It is a trusted [system](#) providing seamless access to data and interoperable [services](#). It supports the whole research [data life-cycle](#), from discovery and mining to storage, [management](#), [analysis](#) and re-use across borders and disciplines.

Note 2 to entry: It consists of a set of interacting [components](#) ([actors](#), [services](#), [data](#), [policies](#), [processes](#) and [infrastructures](#)) that are distinguished between low variety ([EOSC-Core](#)) and high variety ([EOSC-Exchange](#)).

[SOURCE: Candela, L., Mangione, D. (2020). *Towards a Coherent and Shared Glossary for the European Open Science Cloud*.

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wj9u8QWuCING1O3Lf_yWQJWftXhQwkN_4LzCz48feSQ/edit?usp=sharing, modified – reference to federation of systems.]

3.75

European Open Science Cloud Association

EOSC Association

international non-profit [organisation](#) (AISBL) recognised as the contractual body for the [EOSC Partnership](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board. (2020). Draft proposal for a European Partnership under Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he_partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf, modified – reference to organisation instead of association.]

3.76

external platform

industry platform

platform

[ICT infrastructure](#) that consists in a set of stable (low variety) [components](#) providing the foundation upon which the [actors](#) of an [ecosystem](#) can develop complementary products, technologies, or [services](#), and that has the potential of creating network effects.

3.77

FAIR data

[data](#) that conform to the [FAIR principles](#).

3.78

FAIR digital object

FDO

[digital object](#) that conforms to the [FAIR principles](#).

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia.

<https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>.]

FAIR guiding principles

see [FAIR principles](#).

3.79

FAIR principles

FAIR guiding principles

set of guiding lines to make [data](#) Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

[SOURCE: COMMISSION DECISION of 27.8.2018 Setting up the Expert Group - Executive Board of the European Open Science Cloud ('EOSC') and laying down rules for its financing.]

FDO

see [FAIR digital object](#).

3.80

federated architecture

architecture of a [federation of systems](#).

3.81

federated data

[data onboarded](#) by a [federation member](#).

federated ecosystem

see [federation](#).

3.82

federated identity

[identity](#) that is meaningful and trusted within a [federation](#).

[SOURCE: Lee, C. A., Bohn, R. B., & Michel, M. (2020). *The NIST Cloud Federation Reference Architecture* (NIST SP 500-332). National Institute of Standards and Technology.
[https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-332.](https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-332)]

3.83

federated infrastructure

set of [infrastructures](#), or part of them, shared by [federation members](#) through [federating services](#).

Note 1 to entry: A federated infrastructure can include other federated infrastructures.

Note 2 to entry: A federated infrastructure is inherently distributed.

3.84

federated resource

[resource](#) that is being made available by a [federation member](#) such that discovery and access can be managed as part of the [federation](#).

[SOURCE: Lee, C. A., Bohn, R. B., & Michel, M. (2020). *The NIST Cloud Federation Reference Architecture* (NIST SP 500-332). National Institute of Standards and Technology.
[https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-332.](https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-332)]

3.85

federated service

[IT service onboarded](#) by a [federation member](#).

federating core

see [EOSC-Core](#).

3.86

federating service

federation service

horizontal service

pre-production environment service

[IT service](#) required to onboard, discover, share, access or re-use the [resources](#) that a [federation member](#) is willing to share.

Note 1 to entry: Federation services include the [EOSC Portal](#) and [accounting](#), [authentication and authorisation infrastructure](#), [orchestration](#), [helpdesk](#), [monitoring](#) and [PID services](#).

3.87

federation

federated ecosystem

[ecosystem](#) in which multiple [actors](#), the [federation members](#), jointly contribute to the delivery of [resources](#) to [end-users](#).

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). Part 0: Overview and vocabulary (2.4).

<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>, modified – reference to ecosystem; reference to actor; reference to end-users instead of customers; the organisation reference has been removed; reference to resources instead of services.]

3.88

federation member

[actor](#) that works together with other federation members in a [federation](#) to provide one or more [resources](#).

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). Part 0: Overview and vocabulary (2.4).

<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>, modified – reference to actor; Note has been removed; reference to resources instead of services.]

3.89

federation of systems

FoS

[system of systems](#) that rates high on three dimensions of autonomy, heterogeneity, and dispersion.

Note 1 to entry: Each component system is provided by a [federation member](#) who chooses of its own accord to participate in the [federation](#) and the FoS as it sees fit. It is a “coalition of the willing.”

Note 2 to entry: The attributes of autonomy, heterogeneity, and distribution are interrelated. As power shifts from central direction to more collaborative management of development and operations, the characteristics can change by degree. As control is decentralized and localized, then local requirements and local interpretations can become more diversified. Local power with autonomy contributes to variations in requirements and therefore system capabilities supporting these. Similarly, greater geographic dispersion can contribute to increased autonomy, which results in more localization of processes, concepts, and even cultures. These, in turn, can lead to singular requirements, which in turn leads to more heterogeneity.

[SOURCE: Federation of Systems (FoS) (glossary). (15 May 2020). *SEBoK*, .

[https://sebokwiki.org/w/index.php?title=Federation_of_Systems_\(FoS\)__\(glossary\)&oldid=59476](https://sebokwiki.org/w/index.php?title=Federation_of_Systems_(FoS)__(glossary)&oldid=59476), modified – references to federation member and federation]

federation service

see [federating service](#).

FoS

see [federation of systems](#).

3.90

free at the point of use

service payment model where the [end-user](#) does not pay directly for the [service](#) when it is delivered but their consumption will be paid for by other means.

EXAMPLE An end-user would not need to use a credit card to pay for a service but their employer may receive an annual bill from the [service provider](#), or the employer has arranged a suitable subscription.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Sustainability Working Group. (2020). Solutions for a sustainable EOSC: A FAIR Lady (olim Iron Lady) report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/870770>, modified – reference to service payment model.]

3.91

General Assembly

supreme authoritative body of the [governance structure](#) that has all powers except those expressly reserved or delegated to the other bodies of the [EOSC Association](#) by the Code of companies and associations, the Statutes or by a decision passed by itself.

Note 1 to entry: The General Assembly is composed of one Delegate per [Member](#) and one Representative per [Observer](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL. https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf, modified – reference to body of the governance structure.]

3.92

generic repository

[repository](#) directed to all research disciplines.

[SOURCE: Wittenburg, P. (2019). Role of Repositories in Research Infrastructure Building [Repository Topic Group Report].]

generic service

see [common service](#).

3.93

governance

[process](#) of establishing and enforcing strategic goals and objectives, organizational policies and performance parameters.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017.]

3.94

governance structure

set of bodies of the [EOSC Association](#) responsible for the [governance](#) of [EOSC](#).

3.95

helpdesk

[IT service](#) for enabling and managing support requests from [users](#).

Note 1 to entry: It supports incident and service request management to restore normal/agreed service operation within the agreed time after the occurrence of an incident, and to respond to user service requests.

Note 2 to entry: The [service](#) works as a unified ticketing system, by connecting individual providers' helpdesks to the central helpdesk instance, offering a standalone service interface.

[SOURCE: Note 1 and 2 to entry: Donvito, G., Scardaci, D., Sanden, M. V. D., Nicotri, S., & Costantini, A. (2019). *D10.4 EOSC Hub Technical Architecture and standards roadmap v2*. <https://documents.egi.eu/public/RetrieveFile?docid=3495&filename=EOSC-hub%20D10.4%20v2%20Under%20EC%20review%20Public.pdf&version=4>]

high performance computing

see [high-performance computing](#).

high performance computing infrastructure

see [high-performance computing infrastructure](#).

high throughput computing

see [high-throughput computing](#).

high throughput computing infrastructure

see [high-throughput computing infrastructure](#).

3.96

high-performance computing

high performance computing

HPC

computing [paradigm](#) that focuses on the efficient execution of compute intensive, tightly-coupled tasks. Given the high parallel communication requirements, the tasks are typically executed on low latency interconnects which makes it possible to share data very rapidly between a large number of processors working on the same problem. HPC systems are delivered through low

latency clusters and supercomputers and are typically optimised to maximise the number of operations per seconds. The typical metrics are FLOPS, tasks/s, I/O rates.

[SOURCE: *Glossary V3—EGIWiki*. https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Glossary_V3.]

3.97

high-performance computing infrastructure

high performance computing infrastructure

HPC infrastructure

[computing infrastructure](#) enabling [high-performance computing](#).

3.98

high-throughput computing

high throughput computing

HTC

computing [paradigm](#) that focuses on the efficient execution of a large number of loosely-coupled tasks. Given the minimal parallel communication requirements, the tasks can be executed on clusters or physically distributed resources using grid technologies. HTC systems are typically optimised to maximise the throughput over a long period of time and a typical metric is jobs per month or year.

[SOURCE: *Glossary V3—EGIWiki*. https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Glossary_V3.]

3.99

high-throughput computing infrastructure

high throughput computing infrastructure

HTC infrastructure

[computing infrastructure](#) enabling [high-throughput computing](#).

horizontal service

see [federating service](#).

HPC

see [high-performance computing](#).

HPC infrastructure

see [high-performance computing infrastructure](#).

HTC

see [high-throughput computing](#).

HTC infrastructure

see [high-throughput computing infrastructure](#).

ICT infrastructure

see [information and communication technology infrastructure](#).

3.100

identity

set of attributes related to an [user](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 24760-1:2019, modified – reference to user instead of entity]

3.101

identity federation

[federation](#) that is exclusively concerned with managing [federated identities](#).

[SOURCE: Lee, C. A., Bohn, R. B., & Michel, M. (2020). *The NIST Cloud Federation Reference Architecture* (NIST SP 500-332). National Institute of Standards and Technology.

<https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.500-332.>]

3.102

identity provider

IdP

[service provider](#) that creates, maintains and manages trusted identity information of [end-users](#) and offers identity-based services based on trust, business and other types of relationship.

[SOURCE: ITU-T X.1255, modified – reference to service provider instead of entity; reference to end-users instead of other entities.]

IdP

see [identity provider](#).

IF

see [interoperability framework](#).

industry platform

see [external platform](#).

3.103

information

[data](#) that are processed, organized and correlated to produce meaning.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 20547-3:2020.]

3.104

information and communication technology infrastructure

ICT infrastructure

[digital infrastructure](#) including all categories of ubiquitous technology used for the gathering, storing, transmitting, retrieving, or processing of information (e.g., microelectronics, printed circuit boards, computing systems, software, signal processors, mobile telephony, satellite communications, and networks).

[SOURCE: DoDI 5200.44, modified – reference to digital infrastructure.]

3.105
information technology infrastructure
IT infrastructure

[ICT infrastructure](#) consisting of all the technical components, system software, databases and data files and deployed application software, technical procedures, and technical documentation used to make the information available.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 16350:2015, modified – reference to ICT infrastructure.]

3.106
information technology service
IT service

[service](#) that is enabled by the use of information technology (IT).

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). *Part 0: Overview and vocabulary* (2.4).
<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>]

3.107
infrastructure

[system](#) of facilities, equipment and [services](#) needed for the operation of an [organization](#).

EXAMPLE All the facilities, hardware and software required to deliver a [repository](#); the repository itself can be seen both as a service, if it is used directly by an [end-user](#), or as an infrastructure, if it is used as a [component](#) in a more complex system.

Note 1 to entry: Infrastructure is a relational concept: a component becomes an infrastructure when it is needed in order to enable a service that otherwise could not be offered.

[SOURCE: ISO 9000:2015, modified – example and Note 1 to entry have been added.]

3.108
institutional repository
IR

[repository](#) serving a single [organisation](#).

Note 1 to entry: Often are generic, multisubject repositories; for example, within a university.

[SOURCE: CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2019). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements: Glossary 2020–2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3632563>, modified – reference to single organisation instead of research performing institution.]

3.109
interoperability

ability of two or more [systems](#) to exchange [information](#) and to make mutual use of the information that has been exchanged.

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017, modified – Note 1 to entry has been removed.]

3.110
interoperability framework
IF

EOSC interoperability framework

set of recommendations on the [components](#) that need to be provided in the [ecosystem](#) and on the principles guiding digital object producers and/or [consumers](#) on their use.

Note 1 to entry: The role of interoperability frameworks is to “define community practices for data sharing, data formats, metadata standards, tools and [infrastructure](#), recognising the objectives and cultures of different research communities

[SOURCE: Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M., Choirat, C., Sanden, M. van de, & Coppens, F. (2020). *EOSC Interoperability Framework* (Draft for Community Consultation v1.0). EOSC Executive Board, FAIR Working Group and Architecture Working Group.]

IR

see [institutional repository](#).

IT infrastructure

see [information technology infrastructure](#).

IT service

see [information technology service](#).

3.111
knowledge

maintained, processed, and interpreted [information](#).

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017.]

3.112

legal entity

[organisation](#) that has been established in accordance with the laws and customs of the country of origin or that has been constituted as an intergovernmental organisation pursuant to an international treaty in accordance with principles of international law. It cannot be a department of national governments or ministries.

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL.

https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf, modified – reference to organisation.]

3.113

legal interoperability

ability to combine [data](#) from two or more sources without conflicts among restrictions imposed by data providers (i.e., support of one restriction inherently negates support of another) and without having to seek authorization from the data providers on a case-by-case basis.

Note 1 to entry: Legal interoperability among multiple [datasets](#) from different sources occurs when: the legal use conditions are clearly and readily determinable for each of the datasets typically through automated means; the legal use conditions imposed on each dataset allow creation and use of combined or derivative products; and [users](#) may legally access and use each dataset without seeking authorization from data creators on a case-by-case basis assuming that the accumulated conditions of use for each and all of the datasets are met.

[SOURCE: Doldirina, C., Eisenstadt, A. R., Onsrud, H., & Uhler, P. F. (2016). Legal Approaches for Open Access to Research Data.]

machine actionable

see [machine-actionable](#).

machine readable

see [machine-readable](#).

3.114

machine-actionable

machine actionable

[machine-readable](#) and also in a form that a computing system may process in some automated fashion.

EXAMPLE Machine-actionable data, machine-actionable policy.

[SOURCE: RDA DFT working group. (2019). DFT Vocabulary 4.0 Philadelphia.

<https://smw-rda.esc.rzg.mpg.de/dft-4.0.html>, modified – reference to machine-readable.]

3.115

machine-readable
machine readable

in a form that can be identified, recognised and extracted by a computer.

[SOURCE: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary. <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/>, modified – reference to identified, recognised and extracted instead of used and understood.]

3.116

Mandated Organisation

<EOSC Association> [Member](#) appointed by a Member State or an Associated Country to represent national interests or appointed by the EIROforum to represent the views of the Forum

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL.
https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf.]

3.117

Member

<EOSC Association> European-only [legal entity](#) admitted to the [EOSC Association](#) with full rights

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL.
https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf.]

3.118

metadata

[data](#) defining and describing other data.

Note 1 to entry: Metadata can be categorised as [descriptive](#), [structural](#), [preservation](#) and [administrative metadata](#).

[SOURCE: ISO 8000-2:2020, modified – Note 1 to entry has been added; ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified – reference to preservation metadata.]

3.119

Minimum Viable EOSC

MVE

initial implementation of [EOSC](#) that brings [value](#) to [users](#) beyond their current use of [infrastructures](#).

Note 1 to entry: The MVE includes [EOSC-Core](#) and [EOSC-Exchange](#) that work with the FAIR datasets to be federated via EOSC.

Note 2 to entry: Despite the similarities the MVE is a distinct concept from the minimum viable product (MVP).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Sustainability Working Group. (2020). *Solutions for a sustainable EOSC: A FAIR Lady (olim Iron Lady) report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/870770>.]

3.120 monitoring service

[IT service](#) for enabling [service monitoring](#).

Note 1 to entry: It monitors the availability and reliability of the [services](#) from a high-level view down to individual system metrics and monitors the conformance of multiple [SLAs](#).

Note 2 to entry: The key functional requirements are: Monitoring of services; Reporting availability and reliability; Visualization of the services status; Provide dashboard interfaces; Sending real-time alerts.

[SOURCE: Note 1 and 2 to entry: *Monitoring—EOSC Documentation—EGI Confluence*. <https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSCDOC/Monitoring>.]

MVE

see [Minimum Viable EOSC](#).

OA

see [open access](#).

3.121

Observer

<EOSC Association> [legal entity](#) admitted to the [EOSC Association](#) with limited rights

Note 1 to entry: An Observer cannot vote at the [General Assembly](#) or propose candidates for the [Board](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL. https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf.]

OI

see [open innovation](#).

OI2

see [open innovation 2.0](#).

on-boarding

see [onboarding](#).

3.122

onboarding

on-boarding

[process](#) where inputs characterise a [component](#) and the intended result is the inclusion of that component into the [EOSC](#).

3.123

open access

OA

practice of providing online access to [research outputs](#) free of charge to the [end-user](#).

[SOURCE: Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, 11251/1/20 REV 1. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/45766/st11251-re01-en20.pdf>, modified – resulting from actions funded under the Programme has been omitted.]

3.124

open data

[data](#) in an open format that can be freely used, re-used and shared by anyone for any purpose.

[SOURCE: DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast).]

3.125

open innovation

OI

distributed innovation [process](#) based on purposively managed knowledge flows across organizational boundaries, using pecuniary and non-pecuniary mechanisms in line with the organization's business model.

Note 1 to entry: These flows of [knowledge](#) may involve knowledge inflows to the focal organization (leveraging external knowledge sources through internal processes), knowledge outflows from a focal organization (leveraging internal knowledge through external commercialization processes) or both (coupling external knowledge sources and commercialization activities).

Note 2 to entry: Innovation refers to the development and commercialization of new or improved products, processes or services, while the openness aspect is represented by the knowledge flows across the permeable organizational boundary. As an organizational construct, it is moreover the business model, which may be implicit or explicit, that puts the distributed innovation process into the organizational realm as it describes not only how value is created within the value network but also how it is captured by the involved organization(s).

[SOURCE: Chesbrough, H., & Bogers, M. (2014). Explicating Open Innovation: Clarifying an Emerging Paradigm for Understanding Innovation. In *New Frontiers in Open Innovation*. Oxford University Press. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2427233>.]

3.126

open innovation 2.0

OI2

[open innovation paradigm](#) based on the [quadruple helix innovation model](#).

3.127

open science

approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge.

[SOURCE: Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing Horizon Europe -the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, 11251/1/20 REV 1. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/45766/st11251-re01-en20.pdf>]

3.128

orchestration

type of [composition](#) where one particular [resource](#) is used by the composition to oversee and direct the other resource.

Note 1 to entry: The resource that directs an orchestration is not part of the orchestration (Composition instance) itself.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to resource instead of element; Note 2 to entry has been removed.]

3.129

orchestration service

[IT service](#) for enabling and managing [service orchestration](#).

3.130

organisation

[actor](#) that has its own functions with responsibilities, authorities and relationships to achieve its objectives.

[SOURCE: ISO 9000:2015, modified – Notes to entry have been omitted; reference to actor instead of person or group of people.]

3.131

organisational interoperability

way in which [organisations](#) align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals.

[SOURCE: Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M., Choirat, C., Sanden, M. van de, & Coppens, F. (2020). *EOSC Interoperability Framework* (Draft for Community Consultation v1.0). EOSC Executive Board, FAIR Working Group and Architecture Working Group.]

3.132

paradigm

recognized scientific achievement that for a time provide model problems and solutions to a community of practitioners.

Note 1 to entry: The concept of paradigm implies that some accepted examples of actual scientific practice — examples which include law, theory, application, and instrumentation together — provide models from which spring particular coherent traditions of scientific research.

[SOURCE: Kuhn, T. S. (1970). *The structure of scientific revolutions* (2d ed., enlarged). University of Chicago Press, modified – removed universally (two paradigms can co-exist and co-evolve; see Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. J. (2009). 'Mode 3' and 'Quadruple Helix': Toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 46(3/4), 201. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTM.2009.023374>).]

3.133

persistent identifier

PID

unique identifier that ensures permanent access for a [digital object](#) by providing access to it independently of its physical location or current ownership.

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017]

3.134

PID

see [persistent identifier](#).

3.135

PID authority

[user](#) responsible for maintaining the rules for defining the integrity of [PIDs](#) within a [PID scheme](#).

Note 1 to entry: These rules may include setting standards for lexical formats, algorithms and protocols to ensure global uniqueness, together with setting quality of service conditions to enforce compliance to the rules.

Note 2 to entry: PID authorities may be [organisations](#) (e.g. DOI.org), which enforce control over a [PID infrastructure](#). But there may also be authorities which do not have a central control (for example Software Heritage persistent identifiers and W3C's Decentralized Identifiers), but provide a community standardisation mechanism that specifies the conformance of PIDs to a PID scheme.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud*, modified – reference to user instead of controller.]

3.136

PID infrastructure

[ICT infrastructure](#) consisting of the [components](#) needed for enabling and managing [PIDs](#).

3.137

PID manager

[user](#) who has responsibilities to maintain the integrity of the relationship between [digital objects](#) and their [PIDs](#), in conformance to a [PID scheme](#) defined by a [PID authority](#).

Note 1 to entry: A PID manager will typically subscribe to [PID services](#) to offer functionality to [PID owners](#) within the PID manager's services. One example is a [service provider](#) which uses PID Services as part of its own service delivery. For example, PID managers may include a provider of a [data repository](#), a data catalogue, or a research workflow system.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud*, modified – reference to user; reference to digital objects instead of entities.]

3.138

PID owner

[user](#) who has the authority to create a [PID](#), assign PID to a [digital object](#), provide and maintain accurate kernel information for the PID.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud*, modified – reference to user instead of actor; reference to digital object instead of entity]

3.139

PID scheme

set of rules and standards defining the nature of a [PID](#).

Note 1 to entry: This would include a set of lexical formatting rules for PIDs within a namespace. It could also define for example: associated PID type; definition of associated

metadata; quality assurance conditions; usage rights, terms and conditions, and algorithmic methods for generating PID names and enforcing PID properties.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud.*]

3.140

PID service

[IT service](#) that create, manage and resolve [PIDs](#) and their associated kernel information which conforms to a [PID scheme](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud*, modified – reference to IT service.]

3.141

PID service provider

[service provider](#) which provides [PID services](#) in conformance to a [PID scheme](#), subject to its [PID authority](#).

Note 1 to entry: PID service providers have responsibility for the provision, integrity, reliability and scalability of PID services, in particular the issuing and resolution of PIDs, but also lookup and search services, and interoperability with a generic resolution system.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, FAIR and Architecture Working Groups. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud*, modified – reference to service provider instead of organisation.]

platform

see [external platform](#).

3.142

policy

documented set of intentions, expectations, goals, rules and requirements, often formally expressed by top management representatives in an [organisation](#) or [federation](#).

Note 1 to entry: Policies are then realised in [processes](#), which are in turn made up of activities that people carry out according to defined procedures.

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). *FitSM-0: Overview and Vocabulary*.
<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>.]

3.143

policy maker

[user](#) who gathers [information](#) through consultation and research and reduces and extracts from the information, a [policy](#), set of policies or a strategic framework which serve to promote what is the preferred course of action and could include financial support to research.

EXAMPLE The governing board of a Public Health Directorate who provides information from clinical practice and gets the incidence trends of a specific disease to implement their healthcare plans.

Note 1 to entry: [EOSC](#) Skills required: Reasonable knowledge on the EOSC, with special focus on [open science](#), privacy and security and [FAIR principles](#), ability to use EOSC [discipline-specific](#) and [generic services](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to user instead of policy makers.]

pre-production environment service

see [federating service](#).

3.144

preservation metadata

[metadata](#) for supporting the long-term management and future migration or emulation throughout the life-cycle of resources.

EXAMPLE Checksum, hash, [structural metadata](#).

[SOURCE: Riley, J., & National Information Standards Organization (U.S.). (2017). Understanding metadata: What is metadata, and what is it for? <http://www.niso.org/publications/understanding-metadata-riley>, modified – reference to resources instead of digital files; preservation metadata are not considered just administrative metadata, rather they span all metadata categories (see PREMIS Editorial Committee. (2015). *PREMIS Data Dictionary for Preservation Metadata* (version 3.0).).]

3.145

privacy policy

[policy](#) with regard to the processing of personal information in a particular setting.

[SOURCE: ISO/TS 17975:2015, modified – reference to policy instead of specification of objectives, rules, obligations and privacy controls]

3.146

process

set of interrelated or interacting [activities](#) that use inputs to deliver an intended result.

Note 1 to entry: Whether the “intended result” of a process is called output, product or [service](#) depends on the context of the reference.

Note 2 to entry: Inputs to a process are generally the outputs of other processes and outputs of a process are generally the inputs to other processes.

Note 3 to entry: Two or more interrelated and interacting processes in series can also be referred to as a process.

[SOURCE: ISO 9000:2015, modified – Notes 4, 5 and 6 to entry have been omitted.]

3.147**processed data**

[data](#) which have been transformed from [raw data](#) or from an earlier data stage into a more refined stage by [data cleaning](#), sorting, linking, verifying and similar operations.

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017]

3.148**provenance metadata****context metadata**

[administrative metadata](#) describing the lifecycle of a [resource](#) to a point, including the related entities and [processes](#).

EXAMPLE Configuration and log files.

[SOURCE: ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified – reference to resource.]

3.149**provider****resource provider**

[user](#) that manages and delivers a [resource](#) or resources.

provider on-boarding

see [provider onboarding](#).

3.150**provider onboarding****provider on-boarding****resource provider onboarding****resource provider on-boarding**

[onboarding](#) where inputs characterise a [provider](#) and the intended result is the inclusion of that provider into the [EOSC](#).

3.151

quadruple helix innovation model

non-linear interaction model in an [ecosystem](#) consisting of government, academic, industry and media-based and culture-based public stakeholders.

3.152

raw data

[data](#) in its originally acquired, direct form from its source before subsequent [processing](#).

[SOURCE: ISO 5127:2017.]

3.153

repository

data repository

digital repository

archive

[IT service](#) for [managing](#) and [curating data](#), enabling their long-term preservation and reuse.

3.154

research data

[data](#) collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities and used as evidence in the research process, or commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results.

[SOURCE: DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), modified – reference to data.]

3.155

research data repository

[repository](#) aimed at certain research domains, disciplines or communities.

[SOURCE: Lehvslaiho, H., Parland-von Essen, J., Behnke, C., Laine, H., Riungu-Kalliosaari, L., Le Franc, Y., & Staiger, C. (2019). D2.1 Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3557381>, modified – reference to disciplines.]

research funder

see [research funding organisation](#).

3.156

research funding organisation

RFO

research funder

[organisation](#) which funds research.

[SOURCE: Reinhardt, A., & Milzow, K. (2012). Evaluation in Research and Research Funding Organisations: European Practices. European Science Foundation.

<https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2012.97>, modified reference to organisation instead of governmental agency or private organisation.]

research information management system

see [current research information system](#).

3.157

research infrastructure

RI

[infrastructure](#) that provides [resources](#) for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields.

Note 1 to entry: This definition includes the associated human resources, and it covers major equipment or sets of instruments; knowledge-related facilities such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures; computing systems, communication networks, and any other infrastructure, of a unique nature and open to external users, essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation.

Note 2 to entry: Where relevant, it may be used beyond research, for example for education or public services.

Note 3 to entry: It may be 'single sited', 'virtual' or 'distributed'.

[SOURCE: Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, 11251/1/20 REV 1. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/45766/st11251-re01-en20.pdf>, modified – reference to infrastructure instead of facility; reference to resources instead of resources and services.]

3.158

research output

result of scientific research activities to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, [data](#) or other engineered outcomes and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols and electronic notebooks.

[SOURCE: Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, 11251/1/20 REV 1. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/45766/st11251-re01-en20.pdf>, modified – reference to result of scientific research activities instead of results generated by the action]

3.159

research performing organisation

RPO

[organisation](#) which is itself realising research and which employs active [researchers](#).

[SOURCE: Reinhardt, A., & Milzow, K. (2012). Evaluation in Research and Research Funding Organisations: European Practices. European Science Foundation. <https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2012.97>, modified – reference to organisation instead of institution or organisation.

3.160

research software engineer

[user](#) who is an Information and Communication Technologies expert that designs, implements and/or integrates [EOSC services](#) for [data management](#) and [processing](#), according to software quality and FAIR-by-design principles.

EXAMPLE An expert on ICT that builds a cloud orchestration service to deploy [resources](#) in the cloud to process the [data](#) that is accessed by a user duly authorized by the [AAI \(Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure\)](#).

Note 1 to entry: EOSC Skills required: Ability to implement and use [EOSC-Core](#) and [EOSC exchange](#) services; Understanding of the requirements to manage EOSC FAIR data principles.

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbC1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to user.]

3.161

researcher

[user](#) who uses [EOSC](#) to obtain, process, produce, deposit and share [research data](#), using mainly the [services](#) provided by the EOSC.

EXAMPLE A researcher that requests through a portal to run a phylogenetic study on the samples in the different genetic variants of the flu available in an EOSC [repository](#), visualizes it

in a phylogenetic tree and pastes the image on an article she is writing, referencing the data sources and processing pipelines.

Note 1 to entry: EOSC Skills required: General knowledge on the EOSC (including FAIR principles), ability to use EOSC [discipline-specific services](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Skills & Training Working Group, Minimum EOSC Skill Set Task Force. (2020). *EOSC actors profiles diagram*.
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AMvbc1ZIJXddUXatIPgnZlphbrppSSda/view>, modified – reference to user.]

3.162

resource

EOSC resource

<EOSC> any [component](#) available by [EOSC](#).

Note 1 to entry: Resources are listed publicly, comply with policy requirements (for example on openness of publicly funded data) and are findable without charge by all [users](#).

[SOURCE: Note 1 to entry: EOSC Executive Board, Rules of Participation Working Group. (2020). *Rules of Participation* (Version 0.5).
https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/draft_eosc_rop_version_0.5_20-10-2020.pdf]

3.163

resource

<system> asset that is utilized or consumed during the execution of a [process](#)

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC/IEEE 24748-1:2018, modified – Notes to entry have been omitted.]

3.164

resource composability

ability to [compose resources](#) (e.g. computing, storage, services, data sources, datasets, publications or other research products) to build solutions by overcoming their heterogeneity and interoperability barriers.

[SOURCE: Executive Board. (2020). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (Version 0.8).
<https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc-sria-v08.pdf>, modified – reference to compose instead of assemble.]

resource on-boarding

see [resource onboarding](#).

3.165

resource onboarding**resource on-boarding**

[onboarding](#) where inputs characterise a [service](#) or [data](#) and the intended result is the inclusion of that service or those data into the [EOSC](#).

resource provider

see [provider](#).

resource provider on-boarding

see [provider onboarding](#).

resource provider onboarding

see [provider onboarding](#).

RFO

see [research funding organisation](#).

RI

see [research infrastructure](#).

3.166**rights metadata**

[administrative metadata](#) defining the ownership and the legally permitted usage of a [resource](#).

Note 1 to entry: Typically describes the agents responsible for the custody and administration of the resource.

[SOURCE: ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified – reference to resource instead of object.]

RIMS

see [current research information system](#).

RoP

see [Rules of Participation](#).

RPO

see [research performing organisation](#).

3.167**Rules of Participation****RoP**

set of [policies](#) defining a minimal set of rights, obligations and accountability governing the activities of the [users](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC Executive Board, Rules of Participation Working Group. (2020). *Rules of Participation* (Version 0.5).

https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/draft_eosc_rop_version_0.5_20-10-2020.pdf, modified – reference to users instead of those using the EOSC.]

3.168

Secretariat

body of the [governance structure](#) that advises and supports the [General Assembly](#) and the [Board](#), coordinates the implementation of their decisions, conducts day-to-day management and administers the finances of the [EOSC Association](#).

[SOURCE: EOSC AISBL Statutes, (2020), FINAL.

https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf, modified – reference to body of the governance structure.]

3.169

semantic interoperability

[interoperability](#) so that the meaning of the data model within the context of a subject area is understood by the participating [systems](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 19941:2017]

3.170

service

means of delivering [value](#) for the [end-user](#) by facilitating outcomes the end-user wants to achieve.

Note 1 to entry: Service is generally intangible.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 20000-10:2018, modified – reference to end-user instead of user; Note 2 to entry has been removed.]

3.171

service composition

[composition](#) that provides (in the operational sense) higher level [services](#) that are only an assembly of other services.

Note 1 to entry: A composition can support different composition patterns, such as collaboration, choreography, [orchestration](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – service assembly as a preferred term has been removed; Note 2 to entry has been removed.]

3.172

service contract

terms, conditions, and interaction rules that interacting [end-users](#) and [service providers](#) agree to (directly or indirectly).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to end-users instead of service consumers; Note 1 and 2 to entry have been omitted.]

3.173

service level agreement

SLA

[service contract](#) that defines measurable conditions of interactions between a [service provider](#) and an [end-user](#).

Note 1 to entry: A service level agreement may specify: the set of [services](#) the service provider will deliver, a sufficient, specific definition of each service, the responsibilities of the service provider and the end-user, the set of metrics to determine whether the service provider is delivering the service as promised, an auditing mechanism to [monitor](#) the service, the remedies available to the end-user and service provider if the terms of the SLA are not met, and how the SLA will change over time.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to end-user instead of service consumer.]

3.174

service level specification

SLS

statement of service levels that can be expected.

Note 1 to entry: It has the same content as an [SLA](#) but more clearly is not a [service contract](#).

[SOURCE: Appleton, O. (2020). *D1.4 EOSC Portal SLA, SRM, Privacy Policy*. <https://repository.eosc-portal.eu/index.php/s/nEsxySAFMZJizwH>, modified – reference to service contract instead of agreement.]

3.175

service management

[process](#) of [monitoring](#), controlling, maintaining, optimizing, and operating [services](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to process.]

3.176

service monitoring

service management activities of tracking state and operational conditions related to the execution, performance, and real-world effects of [services](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to service management activities.]

service on-boarding

see [service onboarding](#).

3.177**service onboarding****service on-boarding**

[resource onboarding](#) where inputs characterise a [service](#) and the intended result is the inclusion of that service into the [EOSC](#).

3.178**service orchestration**

[orchestration](#) where the orchestrated [resources](#) are [services](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 18384-1:2016, modified – reference to resources instead of elements.]

3.179**service provider**

[provider](#) that manages and delivers a [service](#) or services to [end-users](#).

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). Part 0: Overview and vocabulary (2.4).

<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>, modified – reference to provider instead of organisation or part of an organisation; reference to end-users instead of customers; the federation references have been removed.]

3.180**service providing organisation**

[organisation](#) or part of an organisation that manages and delivers a [service](#) or services to [end-users](#).

[SOURCE: FITSM. (2016). Part 0: Overview and vocabulary (2.4).

<https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>, modified – reference to end-users instead of customers; the federation references have been removed.]

SLA

see [service level agreement](#).

SLS

see [service level specification](#).

**3.181
stakeholder**

[actor](#) that can affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision or activity.

EXAMPLE Customers, owners, people in an [organization](#), [providers](#), bankers, regulators, unions, partners or society that can include competitors or opposing pressure groups.

[SOURCE: ISO 9000:2015, modified – Note 1 to entry has been removed; reference to actor instead of person or organization.]

**3.182
structural metadata**

[metadata](#) that describes how compound [resources](#) are constructed together to make up logical units.

[SOURCE: ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified — reference to metadata instead of information; reference to resources instead of objects.]

**3.183
subject-based repository**

[disciplinary repository](#) aimed at a specific subject.

**3.184
syntactic interoperability**

[interoperability](#) such that the formats of the exchanged [information](#) can be understood by the participating [systems](#).

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 19941:2017]

**3.185
system**

set of different [components](#) so connected or related as to perform a unique function not performable by the components alone ([emergent behaviour](#)).

[SOURCE: Krygiel, A. J. (1999). *Behind the wizard's curtain: An integration environment for a system of systems*. National Defense University.

http://www.dodccrp.org/files/Krygiel_Wizards.pdf, modified – reference to components instead of elements; reference to emergent behaviour.]

**3.186
system of systems
SOS**

[system](#) developed by combining existing systems thus to guarantee (a) *Operational independence* (if the system-of-systems is disassembled into its component systems, the component systems must be able to usefully operate independently); (b) *Managerial independence* (the component systems are separately acquired and integrated but maintain a continuing operational existence independent of the system-of-systems); (c) *Evolutionary development* (the system-of-systems does not appear fully formed. Its development and existence is evolutionary with functions and purposes added, removed, and modified with experience); (e) [Emergent behavior](#) (the system performs functions and carries out purposes that do not reside in any component system. These behaviors are emergent properties of the entire system-of-systems and cannot be localized to any component system. The principal purposes of the systems-of-systems are fulfilled by these behaviors); (v) *Geographic distribution* (the geographic extent of the component systems is large. Large is a nebulous and relative concept as communication capabilities increase, but at a minimum it means that the components can readily exchange only information and not substantial quantities of mass or energy).

[SOURCE: Maier, M. W. (1996). *Architecting Principles for Systems-of-Systems* INCOSE International Symposium, Vol. 6, Issue 1, doi: [10.1002/j.2334-5837.1996.tb02054.x](https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2334-5837.1996.tb02054.x).]

TDR

see [trusted digital repository](#).

3.187

technical interoperability

[interoperability](#) based on standardizing [infrastructure](#), including messaging and transport protocols, message sets and sequencing, encryption, certificates, access controls, digital worklists, and status tracking.

[SOURCE: ISO 21860:2020]

3.188

technical metadata

[administrative metadata](#) describing the technical characteristics of a [resource](#).

EXAMPLE Format, size.

[SOURCE: ISO/TR 14873:2013, modified – reference to resource instead of digital object.]

3.189

technology readiness level

TRL

measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology.

Note 1 to entry: Each technology project is evaluated against the parameters for each technology level and is then assigned a TRL rating based on the projects progress. There are nine technology readiness levels. TRL 1 is the lowest and TRL 9 is the highest.

[SOURCE: *Technology Readiness Level* | NASA.

https://www.nasa.gov/directorates/heo/scan/engineering/technology/txt_accordion1.html

3.190

thematic infrastructure

[infrastructure](#) enabling domain-specific [services](#).

EXAMPLE ELIXIR (The European Life-Science Infrastructure for Biological Information)

Note 1 to entry: Domain examples are: Biomedical Science, Environment and Earth Sciences, Physics and Analytical Facilities, Social Science and Humanities, Astronomy, Energy.

3.191

thematic service

vertical service

community-specific [IT service](#).

EXAMPLE Examples of thematic services are those that store data resources and software tools to access, study and compare the data; data brokering services tailored to the needs of specific scientific communities.

[SOURCE: Donvito, G., Scardaci, D., Sanden, M. V. D., Nicotri, S., & Costantini, A. (2019).

D10.4 EOSC Hub Technical Architecture and standards roadmap v2.

<https://documents.eui.eu/public/RetrieveFile?docid=3495&filename=EOSC-hub%20D10.4%20v2%20Under%20EC%20review%20Public.pdf&version=4>, modified – reference to IT service;

reference to services that store data resources instead of data resource]

TRL

see [technology readiness level](#).

3.192

TRUST principles

set of guidelines to make [digital repositories](#) suitable for [data](#) and [FAIR digital objects](#) management and long-term preservation based on transparency, responsibility, user community, sustainability and technology.

[SOURCE: Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. et al. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), 144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.]

3.193

trusted digital repository
trustworthy digital repository
TDR

[certified repository](#) according to the standard ISO 16363 or the CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements.

trustworthy digital repository
see [trusted digital repository](#).

3.194
use metadata

[administrative metadata](#) that manages [user](#) access, user tracking, and multi-versioning information.

Note 1 to entry: While overlapping [rights metadata](#) in some aspects, use metadata differs in that it can be learned over time, i.e. through tracking downloads, etc.

[SOURCE: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary. <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/>, modified – reference to administrative metadata; Note 1 to entry has been added.]

3.195
user

[actor](#) that interacts with the [EOSC](#) or benefits from the EOSC during its utilization.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015, modified – reference to actor instead of individual or group; reference to EOSC; Note 1 to entry has been removed.]

3.196
value

importance, benefit or usefulness.

EXAMPLE Monetary value, achieving service outcomes, achieving service management objectives, end-user retention, removal of constraints.

Note 1 to entry: The creation of value from [services](#) includes realizing benefits at an optimal resource level while managing risk. An asset and a service are examples that can be assigned a value.

[SOURCE: ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018, modified – reference to end-user instead of customer.]

value added service

see [added-value service](#).

value-added service

see [added-value service](#).

VAS

see [added-value service](#).

vertical service

see [thematic service](#).

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